

UNDERSTANDING THE PATTERN OF EXISTENCE

Dr. NANDESH MOHAN P.* & CHANDRIKA URS P.**

*Associate Professor, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Ayurveda College, and Hospital,
Hassan, Karnataka, India, Email: dr.srinanden@gmail.com

Mobile number of the corresponding author: +91 7204442020

**Assistant Professor, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Ayurveda College, and Hospital,
Hassan, Karnataka, India. Email: chandrikaumeshurs@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

We all have questions about how the entire universe came to be, including ourselves and the entire human race, for which we have been searching for answers for ages. Currently, the big bang theory for the origin of our universe is being popularized. But the assumption that the entire universe started from a singularity, that is a point of infinite density and heat, is not correct, it is purely due to mathematical extrapolation. The singularity (hypothetically containing all of space) is not a physical thing, and it's not really the Big Bang theory either. The Big Bang is not the starting point of the universe, but an event after it. Cosmic inflation occurred in just 10^{-32} seconds from the beginning, and in the epoch of inflation, a gradual expansion begins. Parallel to this description thousands of years ago, according to the *SankhyaDarshanas*, *SrushtiUtpathi* was mentioned from *Prakruthidravayas* i.e., *Avyaktha*, *Mahat*, and *Ahankara*. It is quite intuitive that without the advent of modern sophisticated technologies like the Hubble telescope or the CMB telescopes, how could our *Rishis* conceptualize the origin of the universe thousands of years ago. Perhaps it must be from their familiar experiences of waking, dreaming, and deep sleep; basic experiences that every day could lead them to derive an elaborate account of how this universe could have come into being. These experiences are *AvasthaTraya* explained in the *Mandukya Upanishad* to point to the fourth, which is the consciousness that experiences these experiences. Through this article, a humble attempt is made to understand how our daily experience of waking, dreaming and deep sleep can be extrapolated to understand the pattern of existence.

Keywords: Pattern of Existence, Big Bang Theory, Cosmic Inflation, Avyaktha, Mahat, Ahankara, Mandukya Upanishad, Advaita Vedanta.

1. Introduction:

Understanding why the world is the way it is a remarkable journey from the outside in and expression from the inside out. This article will convey my attempt to find answers to some of the fundamental questions about our own existence and expression around us in this universe. Understanding lies in our own experience. Let us know what our experience is.

2. Avastha Thraya:

We experience the external world through our sense organs. When we are awake, these sense organs are active and interacting with the outside world. This interaction creates perceptions and we develop our own view of the world. Our experiences will be filtered through the reticular activating system, which helps to take only the necessary information with us and formulate the world with our perceptions and beliefs, and there is no way to take sensory perceptions as they are. A waking experience is therefore a state in which you are fully identified with your gross

body through your senses. He who is the "awakening" (*Atma*-Self) in the waking state is called *Vishva*.

Our next phase is in our minds. It's the dream phase. In this stage, we develop worlds in our mind. At this stage, we will be present and from our perception space, time, objects and people will all interact and this is all happening in our mind. We feel sensations in dreams through our mind and sometimes react to them. When we dream, our muscles twitch; we talk out loud or even walk. They are the reactions of the body from sensory perceptions that take place in dreams. And when we come out of dreams, we realize that what happened is just a dream. We experience a dream from the perspective of our own self within it, or the dream ego. Although we identify only with a part of it, the dream ego, which centers our experience of the dream world and presents itself as the locus of our awareness, the whole dream world exists only as a content of our awareness. That is a dream state in which you identify with your subtle body (mind) and experience the mental world. *Atma* (Self) is called *Taijasa* in the dream state.

This is followed by a phase of deep sleep. All physical and mental sense perception is turned off and we experience nothing. Consciousness continues in deep sleep: if there were no consciousness at all in deep and dreamless sleep, then you could not have the memory: "I slept well" immediately after waking up. Memory is the recollection of a past experience; when you remember something, you recall an earlier experience and recall it as your own. When you remember sleeping soundly, you recall something from deep sleep, so the state must have been subtly conscious. In deep sleep, you feel like you know nothing because there is no concrete experience, and you sleep happily because your identity with all its problems is temporarily dormant in deep sleep¹. So, in deep sleep you do not identify with the gross or subtle bodies because you are not experiencing anything, therefore you identify with the casual body during deep sleep. All differences are resolved in the causal body, the mind is unmanifested. Hence no experiences in deep sleep. *Atma* (Self) is called *Prajna* in deep sleep.

So, in the waking state the subject appears as the body and the object appears as what we perceive. In dreams, the subjects appear as the dream ego or dream self and the object as the dream world. In deep sleep, consciousness does not distinguish between subject and object, knower and known. Instead, it rests as one calm "mass". Consciousness withdraws into itself while its function of directing to external objects sleeps. Yet this dormancy is not a complete loss or oblivion of consciousness; it is a peaceful absorption that offers a foretaste of the clear bliss belonging to a self-realized consciousness freed from illusion [1].

These experiences are basic and everyone experiences them and we can have no experience outside of them. In the *Madukya Upanishad*, these *AvasthaTrayahs* are explained to understand that there is a 4th (*Thuriyam*), the underlining self that experiences these three stages and which when experienced is identified as *Vishva*, *Taijasa*, and *Prajna*. The True Self is the 4th which is *SattChittAnanda* (Awareness Existence and Bliss). And in the same *Upanishad* these *Avasthas* are extrapolated to the 3 analytical divisions of the *Pranava Mantra*, i.e., *Aa*, *Uu*, *Mm*. containing *Aum*. So, *Aum* represents these experiences we have every day, and the Self, represents the underlining Silence in which the *Aum mantra* arises and returns to silence.

3. Om Pranava Shabda:

Adi Sankaracharya in the text *Panchikarana* gives an analysis of *Pranava mantra* which shows that it is the seven elements of *Santa* (Retreating into Self), *Sakti* (Sprouting Power), *Bindu* (Logos Kernel), *Bija* (Semnal Sound comprising the Kernel) and then M U A analytical sounds of *Pranava* forming *Nada Om*. The higher degrees are captured by introspection or

contemplation and grouped into Turiya or the Fourth. To these seven degrees of *Pranava* correspond the seven degrees of existence called *Bhu*, *Bhuvan*, *Svar*, *Mahar*, *Jana*, *Tapa* and *Satya*. Corresponding to the four phases of Om Nada, A, U, M, we have the four phases of existence *Stula-A*, *Sukshma-U*, and *Karan-M* of the waking, dreaming, and deep sleep phases and the transcendental *Turiyam*. The fourth is again further divided into *Mahar* (Devotion), *Jana* (Creative), *Tapa* (Contemplative) and *Satya* (True) [2]. The true *Brahman* (*Santa*) conditioned by ignorance with expressed willpower to manifest with *Sakti* develops the locus (*Bindu*) of origin (*Bija*) which expands into the form of *Karana*, *Sukshma* and *Sthula* which become our experiences.

4. *Srushti Utpathi* and Cosmic Evolution:

Now let's see how our experience extrapolates to *Srushti Utpati* and that experience can also bring us closer to understanding why this universe works the way it does. It has been explained in *Advaita* and *Sankhya Darshanas* that *Srushti Utpathi* originates from *Prakruthidravayas*, *Avyaktha*, *Mahat* and *Ahankara*. *Avyaktha* means unmanifested. It is like a person in a deep sleep stage and cannot recognize anything because all his senses are turned off. It is the causal stage in *Beejaroopa* from where everything arises. Although it has the natural light of *Thuriyam*, it is so shrouded in ignorance that it tends to express itself externally³. Similarly, we can approach the creation of the Universe as a kind of inexplicable phenomenon where the entire component for the creation of the Universe was present, but in a tiny potential form, where everything including time and space was ready to explode.

The popular belief of the big bang model is not a theory of how the universe begins. Science does not currently tell us how the universe came to be or what caused it to begin expanding. The assumption of the entire universe started from a singularity, that is a point of infinite density and heat, is not correct; it is purely due to mathematical extrapolation. It is undefined and represents the limit of knowledge. The singularity (hypothetically containing all of space) is not a physical thing, and it's not really the big bang theory either. The Big Bang is not the starting point of the universe, but an event after it.² Basically, the theory says that the universe today is bigger than it was yesterday, and much bigger than it was a billion years ago. As you extrapolate back, the universe gets smaller and smaller, denser and denser, and if you keep going, you get to a very small volume of space that is very dense and very hot. At some point in the extrapolation, the laws of physics stop working because the volume will be zero. All this implies *Avyaktha*, which is not discernible because it is at infinitesimal small scales and near zero time, as in the causal phase of deep sleep, in our conscious experience.

Inflation occurs in the universe shortly after it started exponentially fast, faster than the speed of light, in 10^{-32} seconds and the volume increases by a factor of 10^{78} . This is called cosmic inflation [2]. Although the entire universe may have come from a small volume of space, Cosmic inflation would cause all points in that space to expand. This expansion or inflation has occurred everywhere in the universe. There is no center of location in the universe. Every point has moved away from every other point and every point is the center. In the *Darshnas*, this cosmic inflation is *Mahat*, i.e., the expanse of thoughts, *Budhi*, the principle of intelligence, which is formless, like dreams. In a dream, we also feel it when we are in the middle and everything is happening around us. But when we wake up, everything collapses and it seems like it happened in our mind. All the ingredients for reality will be present in our dreams, but it is not formed as real, we cannot distinguish between reality and dream, similarly in this cosmic

expansion, expanse appears to accommodate space and time and create particles, but it is not yet formed and differentiated.

The scientific theorizes that in the inflationary model inflation is a quantum field that starts with a large amount of vacuum energy. Inflation has occurred and inflation reducing its vacuum energy, closing the inflationary epoch and gradually expanding. At the end of inflation, the inflation subsides and transforms into a flood of elementary particles and radiation. They eventually grew into protons, neutrons, atoms, gas clouds, stars, and galaxies. This matter and radiation achieve their mass (after contact with the Higgs field), reactivity (initial atoms contain only an ionized nucleus very reactive and unstable), and specific qualities with which they combine. This achieves a sense of self-identity where it differentiates itself from self from non-self through its *Gunas* (attributes) & *Karma* (actions) and we interact with these substances. It is *Ahankara*, i.e., the consciousness of approximation and differentiation. This is also the experience we have in our waking state when we interact with matter, approach it and distinguish it, and feel more real.

So, our experience of deep sleep, dreaming and the waking state itself, if extrapolated to *SrushitiUtpathi*, then it is *Avyaktha*, *Mahat*, and *Ahankara* and the currently available theory explains cosmic inflation for the origin of the universe. Our experiences are experienced by the underlying consciousness, and the entire Universe exists in the same consciousness. For this consciousness, the Experience of the Universe is *Avyaktha*, *Mahat* and *Ahankara*, just like our experiences in deep sleep, dreaming, and waking. *Aum* arises from Silence and Silence is Self.

5. *Adyatma, Adibuta, Adidaiva and Satva, Rajas Tamas:*

Three emanations form from the *Ahankara*. In their subjective aspect, *Ahankara* is called *Adyatma* or embodied conditions of the Self. In their objective aspect, they are designated as *Adhibuta*; and the connecting aspect is called *Adhidaiva* (pertaining to the spiritual). These 3 aspects correspond to the triple division of *Ahankara* into *Taijasa*, *Butadi* and *Vaikarika* of the *Sankhya* philosophy and are based on the predominance of things *Rajas* (activity), *Tamas* (dullness), and *Sattva* (luminosity) in the etheric substance of *Ahankara* [3]. *Sattva*, *Rajas*, and *Tamas* are present in everything you see in the universe. In deep sleep all is unmanifest, it is the source of all that is still detached without any attachment, it is *Adidaivika* and hence similar to *Sattva*. In the early stages of the Big Bang, our universe was just a bright opaque light, because where photons were caressed by spinning electrons and light didn't escape. In the dream phase, the Self will have a subjective feeling with the objects of the dream world. It is the expanse of mind with *Rajas*, inflation, movement, propeller for any activity. It is *Adyatma* or *Taijasa*. It is like cosmic inflation with the full activity of creation. In the waking state, interaction with objects in the real world takes place. The objective aspect is described as *Adibuta* is attributed to *Tamas* which means attachments and differentiation. It also means mass, the density attributed to matter. It is similar to the gradual expansion of the universe, cooling and forming atoms, stars and galaxies, dark matter, dark energy, and black holes that attract everything including light.

The *Adhibuta* group of five simple (*Panchtanmatras*) objective principles is further operated by the *Adhidaiva* group to provide another range of ego experiences of the *Adhyatma* group.

So, the experience of waking, dreaming, and deep sleep and how the *Atma* connects is fundamental to experiencing the Universe and is also fundamental to understanding the nature by which matter interacts and identifies itself. *SattChitAnand*, is the source of everything and the expressions of the whole object in the Universe are *Satva Rajas* and *Tamas* the same path to the

Ataman (Self), the expression in terms of experience is the stage of Deep Sleep, Dreaming, and Waking.

6. Fate of the Universe:

We have the history of the universe from 14 billion years ago to the present, but we do not know exactly what the fate of our universe is. According to scientists there are 3 possibilities, one which is called the Big Freeze, when the expansion of the universe overcomes the gravitational force causing all the galaxies to move away from each other as fast as the speed of light and eventually our universes will disappear out of energy and freeze. The 2nd possibility is a Big Rip, in which the gravitational force breaks and exponentially inflates the tearing of not only galaxies, but even the electromagnetic force, a strong force rips off, resulting in the breaking of all the structures of the universe, including atoms. And the last one is the Big Crunch, in which if the gravitational force succeeds in expanding the universe, then it brings all objects, stars, galaxies to one single point after a time similar to the time of the big bang and again it can trigger another big bang and the whole history of the universe can repeat itself. This assumes multiple universes in the form of the Big Bounce [4].

The future of the universe can also be extrapolated by our experiences in everyday life, in the form of waking, dreaming and deep sleep and reawakening, in the same way that the fate of the universe is in a cyclical rhythm similar to what was mentioned as the Big Bounce. Here all phenomena happen in a cyclical way like *Sattva*, *Rajas* and *Tamas* and again *Sattva* or it can end in our death because *Tamas* or *Rajas* can dominate the whole universe and it can die either by Big Freeze or Big Rip.

7. Vasana Forced Desire for *SrishtiUtpathi* and Quantum Tunneling:

तत्सर्वशक्तिबीजजडप्रकृतिवासनायाव्यक्तभावः

प्रणवशब्दः दिककालाणोऽपितस्यरूपाणि ॥३॥ (Braham sutra)

This all-powerful source (seed) created nature with expressed will-power (*Vasana*, desire). *Aum* transforms in space, time and matter (anu, small particles...), etc.

Now we will try to understand in detail how all these materials developed in quantum mechanics. Before the Big Bang, the universe was formed by Quantum Tunneling. This is a real phenomenon that describes a non-zero probability of field formation for nascent particles or crossing the energy barrier threshold to emerge. This is in the *Veda* talking about *Vasana* / the desired power of the *Purusha* (the omnipotent source-Self) to emerge. In quantum mechanics, there is no need for a cause for any phenomenon to happen because there is a presence of non-zero probability for it to occur, and therefore it is the expression of *Purusha's* Desire power in the form of Quantum Tunneling that triggers the formation of everything.

Later, as described earlier in *Aum*, the *Pranava shabda* is all transformed and *Aum* can be expressed as *Aa U Mm* which are again extrapolated as waking, dreaming and deep sleep phases and even *Avyaktha Mahat* and *Ahankara* respectively.

Now among them *Avyaktha* is *Prakruthi* and *Mahat*, *Ahankara* and *Panchatanmatras* are *Prakruthi* and *Vikruthi*. The understanding of *Pakruthi* and *Vikruthi* is unique because the imbalance, if it exists, then only the existence possible, otherwise there is no existence at all. So, what is imbalance, we will understand.

8. Quantum Field Theory:

According to quantum field theory, in the fabric of space and time in a quantum field, fermions and bosons evolve as wave forms. Interactions are determined by spins, and this is again determined by symmetry. Preservation of symmetry is essential for the conservation of quantities such as momentum, angular momentum, energy, and charge. In order to comply with these constraints, the fundamental forces – the electromagnetic force, the weak force, and the strong force – are formed. The material world is made up of fermions and the forces are made up of gauge bosons. Electromagnetic forces are mediated between like-charged particles via photons, and the strong force within the nucleus is mediated by strong binding gluons. These gluons interact with the quarks inside the proton and neutrons, as well as with other gluons. This gluon self-interaction is the reason why the strong force acts like glue instead of a magnet. The charge of the nuclear strong force is the color maintained by Quantum Color Dynamics to bind the quarks within and between protons and neutrons in the nucleus. This color is not a physical color but is given attributes. The weak interaction is the reason for various forms of particle decay. It is weak and short-ranged because the weak intermediary particles, the W and Z bosons, have mass (when interacting with the Higgs field). W bosons have an electric charge and mediate interactions that change the particle type (referred to as flavor) and charge [5].

Bosons and fermions in the early universe, when energy and heat were much higher, created quark gluon plasma. Then, at a lower temperature, the energy potential of the Higgs field changed and a spontaneous symmetry breaking occurred, whereby fermions interacting with the Higgs field acquire a rest mass. This represents 1% of the mass of the total mass of the atom's nucleus. The remaining 99% of the matter comes from the binding energy of the gluon interaction coupled with the strong force between protons and neutrons, followed by chiral symmetry breaking. It is a property of quantum chromodynamics, describing these interactions, responsible for most of the mass (over 99%) of nucleons, and thus all ordinary matter, as it transforms light-bound quarks into 100 times heavier hadrons components⁶. Thus, spontaneous symmetry breaking results in the evolution of matter in particles, and the interaction of these particles with the time and space framework develops gravity. Photons and gluons do not interact with the Higgs field and therefore have no mass.

9. Panchikarana:

When physics talks about the creation of subatomic particles, they are not talking about physical material, but about properties. Similarly, in *Ventanta Darshana Panchatanmatras* are to be understood as constitutional material in terms of properties. They are *Shabda, Sparsha, Roopa, Rasa, Gandha*. These form the *Mahabuta* unit by coming together in a certain ratio called Panchikarana [3]. In *Panchikarana* the entire unit of *Mahabuta* can be divided into 2 halves. One half forms the *Tanmatra* of the respective *Mahabuta* and the other half is equally divided among the four other *Tanmatras*, eg: Unite of *Prathivi Mahabuta* is formed by half of the *Gandhatanmatra* and the other half is equally divided among the other *Tanmatras* like *Shabda, Sparsha, Roopa, Rasa*. The basic idea of the *Panchikarana* of *Panchatanmataras* is how the complexities of materials evolve from the basic materials and also the presence of inherent qualities in all the basic particles with a predominance of one. It is similar to a quantum mechanism in a quantum field, where there is a possibility of the emergence of all possible variants with a greater probability for the development of one.

According to String theory, all subatomic matter consists of strings whose vibrations determine the properties of subatomic particles such as spin, electric charge, color charge, flavors, and

mass. The vibration of the string which determines the rotation can be considered as *Shabdhatatva*. Constraints in the form of rotations following a specific symmetry determine electric charges and electromagnetic force. This can be considered *Saparshatatva*. Together with electric charges, color charges form a strong force according to Boson Chromodynamics. This can be considered as *Roopatatva*. Apart from these fermions are also divided based on flavors like up quarks, down quarks, charm quarks, etc., and specific mass. These can be considered as *Rasatatva* and *Gandhatatva*.

Vacuum space is *Akasha*, it is *Avakasha* for the creation of particles because according to *Panchikarana* it has the potential to create anything. Constraints in the form of rotations to follow a specific symmetry are *Vayu*, because it is the property of *Vayutattva* to induce constraints so that the particles can follow. The interaction caused by these particles in the form of electromagnetic and strong force and generation of the highest degree of temperature is *Agnitatva*. And once it reaches the required energy, it creates the corresponding particles. The quark gluon plasma of all particles in the early universe at the highest degree of temperature can be considered *Jalatatva*. And later, when the temperature decreases and by breaking the symmetry, fermions and bosons gain mass as a result of their interaction to form a strong force and the interaction with the Higgs field can be considered *Pruthvitatva*.

In the history of the universe, it is believed to have occurred about 10^{-12} seconds after the Big Bang, when the universe was too hot. As the universe continued to cool, after 3, 80,000 years electrons get trapped in orbits around nuclei, forming the first atoms.

Spontaneous breaking of symmetry can be understood as a shift from *Prakruthi* to *Prakruthi Vikruthi* thereby causing *Mahat*, *Ahankara*, and *Panchatanmatras* to develop.

So, in physics, the beginnings of the Universe through quantum mechanics expanded into general relativity, and in *Darshana* he explains it from *Avyaktha*, *Mahat*, and *Ahankara* through *Panchikarna*.

10. Unified Theory of Everything and Infinity:

The unified theory, which is the holy grail of physics, the combination of quantum mechanics and general relativity, maybe the mystery of the existence of the universe. Scientists are unable to explain the quantum theory of gravity because it involves the wrapping and fluctuation of space-time itself. When physicists try to quantize gravity, they run into infinities. The infinity that occurred because the field of these fermions and bosons lies on the field of the space-time frame and according to quantum mechanics, such as when electrons and positrons annihilate each other, it generates an energetic photon and transfers back to the evolution of the electron and positron, but in quantum mechanics the uncertainty is such, that a photon can transform into any number of different particles on its way to becoming an electron and a positron [6]. It can do this because the uncertainty principle allows the creation and destruction of any number of virtual particles created by borrowing energy from vacuum space for a very short period of time until the energy changes when the energy is returned to the vacuum. It can do this an infinite number of times before it turns into an electron and a positron. When physicists think about quantum field theory, gravity is not about particles, but about the background where those particles or fields reside. So, when considering the entire infinite number of interactions and annihilations, every possible configuration of space-time under every single possible interaction must be considered and therefore faces infinity and cannot be extrapolated mathematically. Scientists have tried to explain with new theories such as quantum loop theory and string theory,

but these theories are not complete theories that can be explained in terms of observable phenomena. This requires a bold and new approach to understand what our *Darshans* tell about *Atman*, *Paramathma*, *Brahman*, *Purusha* or *Thuriyam*, which is *Anadi* and *Anatha* and its expression is also infinite, one can think about what this space-time field is.

ॐपूर्णमदःपूर्णमिदंपूर्णात्पूर्णमुदच्यते।

पूर्णस्यपूर्णमादायपूर्णमेवावशिष्यते॥(Brihadaranyaka Upanishad)

What is seen is infinity. What is invisible is also infinite. From infinite being came infinity, but only infinity remained.

It may never be possible to reconcile General Relativity with Quantum Mechanics to create a theory of everything, or if possible, they will succumb to the infinity of Objects. Could the universe be a leap from Self-Consciousness (*Purusha*) to its manifestation (*Loka*) through quantum tunneling (*Vasana*).

11. Conclusion:

So, the primary goal of understanding this knowledge through *Pranava* is to truly realize the fundamental unity of consciousness that underlies macroscopic and microscopic manifestation. And also, to think about how our *Rishis* could have achieved this vast knowledge through the familiar experience of waking, dreaming, and deep sleep, the basic experiences that led them to derive an elaborate account of mysteries such as how this universe could have come into being. Modern physicists have sought to understand the universe from the outside as a third-person experience, and therefore believe that consciousness is somehow evolved from non-sentient material. While our *Rishis* could experience through meditation and could analyze them from within as a 1st person's experience, they could therefore conceptualize the origin of the vast universe from the perception of conscious experience and were able to understand that consciousness is fundamental.

References:

- [1] Thompson, Evan. *Waking, Dreaming, Being: new light on the self and Consciousness from neuroscience, meditation, and Philosophy*, Columbia University Press, New York 2015.
- [2] "Big Bang" Wikipedia, Wikimedia Foundation, 15 February 2023, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Big_Bang#Further_reading
- [3] Shankaracharya, Panchikarna with 6 commentaries, Ed by Gajananashambhusadhale, Gujarathi printing press, 1930.
- [4] "Quantum field theory" Wikipedia, Wikimedia Foundation, 23 December 2022 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_field_theory
- [5] "Subatomic particles" Wikipedia, Wikimedia Foundation, 27 November 2022 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Subatomic_particle
- [6] "Elementary Particles" Wikipedia, Wikimedia Foundation, 19 January 2023. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elementary_particle